

Preliminary Report of the Applicability of NIR-Hyperspectral Imaging for Quality Characterization of Texture of Gari/Eba

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Michael ADESOKAN, IITA, Nigeria

Emmanuel ALAMU, IITA, Nigeria

Busie MAZIYA-DIXON, IITA, Nigeria

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Ethics: The activities, which led to the production of this document, were assessed and approved by the CIRAD Ethics Committee (H2020 ethics self-assessment procedure). When relevant, samples were prepared according to good hygiene and manufacturing practices. When external participants were involved in an activity, they were priorly informed about the objective of the activity and explained that their participation was entirely voluntary, that they could stop the interview at any point and that their responses would be anonymous and securely stored by the research team for research purposes.

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This document has been reviewed by

Name SURNAME (Institute's acronym)

DD/MM/YYYY

Final validation by

Name SURNAME (Institute's acronym)

DD/MM/YYYY

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ABSTRACT

The near-infrared hyperspectral images of freshly prepared Gari/Eba produced from 23 cassava genotypes were acquired using the SPECIM FX 17 Camera. Gari/Eba dough was homogenized and placed on the translation stage for a line scan image capture. The hyperspectral image was captured in the 932 to 1721 nm wavelength range and has a spectral resolution of 8 nm. Reflectance calibration and image segmentation were carried out using the Breeze Software (version 2024.1.0) to extract the average spectra from each image. An attempt to predict the textural attributes of Gari/Eba was performed by combining the samples' average spectra with the reference texture values. NIR hyperspectral imaging demonstrated a promising prediction performance for the hardness of Eba but could not accurately predict other textural attributes of Eba. Further attempts will be made by increasing the sample size and extracting the effective wavelengths from the average raw spectra to improve the model's accuracy by removing redundant information. The coefficient of determination in calibration for hardness was 0.93, and a root mean square error of 28.10 g.

Key Words: Gari/Eba, NIR-hyperspectral image, Hardness, PLSR

1 SAMPLING AND MEASUREMENT PROTOCOLS

Freshly harvested cassava roots (23 genotypes) from IITA field trials were processed into Gari, packaged into airtight plastic containers, and transferred to the laboratory for analysis. Eba was produced by reconstituting the gari flakes in boiling water and stirring using a mechanical stirrer until a consistent dough was formed. Eba prepared from each cassava genotype was wrapped in aluminium foil, properly labelled, and transferred into a warmer to prevent heat loss.

2 LABORATORY ANALYSIS

2.1 Instrumental textural analysis

The texture of Eba from each cassava genotype was measured using the TA.XT texturometer following the RTB foods SOP (<https://doi.org/10.18167/agritrop/00604>). Eba was moulded into an adapted sampling cup with a uniform dimension and placed on the sample platform. Textural parameters measured using a TPA profile and a cylindrical probe were hardness, resilience, springiness, adhesiveness and cohesiveness. Samples were measured at a temperature of $45\pm 5^{\circ}\text{C}$.

Figure 1 : TA. XT texturometer

2.2 Hyperspectral imaging analysis

A sub-sample of Eba for image acquisition using the hyperspectral imaging systems, the HSI consist of a 12-bit (CCD camera with a two-dimensional (2D) light detector. It has a spectrograph with high sensitivity from 932 to 1721 nm and a spectral resolution of 8 nm. The samples were placed on the translation Lab Scanner with a dimension of 40 cm x 20 cm (LxW), and the light source was generated from an illumination component made up of 150 W tungsten halogen lamps. The distance of 500 mm was between the halogen lamps and the sample and at an angle of 45 °C to the horizontal plane. The exposure time of the camera and the moving speed in the translation Lab scanner stage was set at 2 ms and 40 mm/s, respectively. White reference was obtained using a white Teflon board with diffuse reflectance of 99% (Spectralon, SRT-99-100, Labsphere Inc, North Sutton, NH, USA) and the dark calibration reference (R_d) with a reference of 0% was obtained by closing the camera shutter.

$$R_s = \frac{R_o - R_d}{R_w - R_d} \dots\dots\dots (Equ.1)$$

where R_s = calibrated reflectance image; R_o = raw hyperspectral image.

R_w = white reference image and R_d = dark reference image.

2.3 Extraction of average spectra from image data cube

The calibrated reflectance image (R_s) for each sample was imported to the Breeze software (version 2024.1.0), and a PCA model was created to analyze the spectral variations in the sample images based on all the pixels in the image to generate the variance scatter plot (Figure 2). Each point in the scatter plot corresponds to pixels in the image, which were clustered based on spectral similarities. The PCA model showed the spectral variance between the sample and the background pixels. PC 1 explains the maximum variance (59.7%) and visualizes the most important spectral variations in the sample image (x-axis of the scatter plot). Also, the raw image spectra contain some non-important and noisy signals, which may be caused by strayed light from the instruments or external interferences from the environment. These signals could affect the identification of relevant spectra information during the modelling process (Osco *et al.* 2022). Several preprocessing algorithms, such as SNV and Savitzky-Golay (SG) and smoothing, were implemented on the raw spectra to eliminate the effects of optical path changes in the original spectra and to eliminate random noise and improve the signal-to-noise ratio (Xu *et al.*, 2023).

Figure 2 : PCA scatter variance of samples and background pixel and the average spectrum of Gari/Eba.

3 RESULTS

The mean values of hardness, resilience, adhesiveness and cohesiveness of Gari/Eba were 355.96, 4.49, 27.88, -529.87 and 0.299 g, respectively (Table 1). The average spectrum of Gari/Eba shows prominent peaks at 194.6 nm and 1433.8 nm, respectively (Figure 3). The raw spectra were subjected to treatments which included standard normal variate and Savitzky-Golay to eliminate noise and correct baseline distortions to improve the signal-to-noise ratio. (Figure 4). An attempt to predict the textural attribute of the Gari/Eba was demonstrated by combining the spectra data matrix (x) and the references variable matrix (y). A total of 42 spectra data points were generated from the samples, which is a relatively small number, to obtain a reliable prediction model. However, the preliminary result shows a promising performance of the model for hardness, with a coefficient of determination of 0.93 and root means square error of 28.10 g (Figure 5).

Table 1 : Statistical summary of texture results of Gari/Eba

Constituents	Type of variable	N	Mean	SD	Minimum	Maximum
Hardness	Quantitative	42	355.9659	110.6268	176.522	616.977
Resilience	Quantitative	42	4.491833	0.901976	3.534	7.406
Springiness	Quantitative	42	27.88074	7.168535	5.703	39.385
Adhesiveness	Quantitative	42	-529.8726	271.5997	-882.669	-75.686
Cohesiveness	Quantitative	42	0.299333	0.040503	0.239	0.396

Figure 3 : Raw spectra preprocessed without pretreatment

Figure 4 : Raw spectra preprocessed using Standard Normal Variate (SNV)

Figure 5 : PLSR model for hardness

4 CONCLUSION

Rapid prediction of textural attributes of RTB food products has become important due to the demand for high-throughput methods to screen large genetic materials. Textural attributes are key drivers of the adoption of new cassava varieties. This study attempts to predict the textural characteristics of gari/Eba using hyperspectral imaging systems. Results showed a good coefficient of determination (R^2) in the calibration of 0.955 for hardness, which is one of the most important textural attributes of the product profile. However, other attributes such as cohesiveness, resilience and springiness have poor R^2 in calibration. This could be due to the small number of genotypes used for the preliminary study. A larger sample size will be explored in the future. Then, the prediction model for Eba's hardness will be validated using an independent set of samples to test the model's performance.

5 REFERENCES

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